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LEADERSHIP MANAGEMENT SKILLS AND PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED PRIVATE HOSPITALS IN ENUGU METROPOLIS

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Abstract: This study looked at the effect of leadership management skills on performance of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis. The specific objectives were to; examine the extent to which conflict resolution affect employee turnover of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis and ascertain the extent to which delegation affect employee productivity of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis. The study adopted a survey design. The population of the study was one hundred and ninety-eight (198). The sample size of 198 was adopted due to manageable unite of the population. The study used convenience sampling procedure and structured questionnaire was used to select respondents. Simple regression analysis tool was employed to test two formulated hypotheses. The findings revealed that conflict resolution had a significant positive effect on employee turnover of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis ($F=1,035$, $pv=.000<0.05$) and delegation channel had a statistically significant positive effect on employee productivity selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis ($F=1,037$, $pv=.008<0.05$). Therefore, based on the findings, researcher also concluded that effective leadership management skills is an important aspect as it usually enables the employees of the organizations to work efficiently and deliver excellent results. The study thus recommends that hospital managers must not relay on their traditional ways of resolving conflict rather they provide modern ways of conflict resolution by initiating conflict resolve panel as a unit of the organization.

Keywords: Leadership management, conflict resolution, employee turnover, delegation, employee productivity

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INTRODUCTION

Globalization competition is inevitable for both developed and developing nations. Businesses devise strategies to outperform the competition by drawing on the resources of their employees, investors, technology, and customers. Because humans are one of the hospital factors of performance, they play an important part in the service delivery and help determine its success level. Therefore, leadership talent (leadership management skills) should be attached to employees because the progress and development of the institutions depend on leadership pattern (Susilo, Furtasan & Uli, 2022).

Leadership skills are very important in the workplace, where a leader must unite subordinates or employees from various divisions to function together and work together. For example, when a team, project, department, or company is having trouble sorting out solutions and deciding on a direction, a leader must be there to organize and make arrangements. In addition, leadership skills are important for people who occupy important positions in the company (top-level management) and for every professional to have these skills so that they become productive team members and can fully contribute to the company (Susilo, et al, 2022).

A Good leadership management skill makes business and not-for-profit organizations successful. In the Nigerian private hospitals, just as any industry, it will be sheer impossible for firms to survive without good leadership. This is shared by Ciulla & Ciulla (2020) who posited that without leadership, organizations move too slowly, stagnate, and lose their way. Leadership is the art of influencing people so that they will strive willingly towards the achievement of goals (Gallos & Bolman, 2021).

In contrast to the measurement tool for leadership management skill (leadership skill) from Kobicheva (2021), which measures virtual devices as a tool for developing leadership skills and the researcher identified the measurement tool for leadership talent using Key Performance Indicators such as Suggestion Rate, Absenteeism, Employee Turnover, Employee Training, Percentage of Responses to Employee Suggestions, Number of Accidents, Employee Productivity, Employee Mutation, Employee Lateness, and Percentage of Health Service Fulfillment (Susilo, et al, 2022).

Organizational performance has gloomy consequences in the organization and to the image of the members. Hylengane and Bayat (2023) study divulge that poor performance corrupt the image of the organization and runs the work place disorderly and disruptive and turnoff employees that are committed to organizational goals. Superior managers faces issues and challenges with task performance because it is a means of measuring how effective the organization leads, whereas subordinate's low performance leads to waste of resources in form of holding cost, high employee redundancy and inability to meet up with client expectation. Moreover, the study seeks to investigate the effect of leadership management skills on performance of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

Management incapability and incapacity to cherish and appreciate its leadership management skills effect on performance leads to poor performance in many private hospitals, the malaise and grievances of performance and lack of effective leadership skills are major problems in most health sectors which many a time or on many numerous occasion results in poor performance. Though not all leaders wish to be collaborative and entrust followers with responsibility due to panic of losing their seat. Predominantly, leaders place much concern with

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what they can get out of performance and profitability, little or no attention given to the subordinates to improve their status. The dissatisfaction of performance leads to a serious drawback to leadership style which constitute to poor growth and development of private hospitals, lack of motivation, persistent complaints strike, etc.

Circumstantially, the Nigerian health sector is considered to be the study because the country constitutes of 200 million populaces comprising of 3% of the world and the management of the private hospitals is seriously in substandard deficient, deplorable and unsatisfactory situation requires urgent and serious attention. However, problem of leadership skills includes lack of adequate staffing thereby not having enough number of staff and supportive resources to provide quality patient care, which has two key elements, that is, having time to listen to patient and being able to discuss patient care problem with other nurses and other staff of the hospitals.

Secondly, leaders in the private hospitals fails to modify their leader skills of leading to the changing situation and business environment, this is so because no one common skills can adequately suit conditions and must give room to change. Leaders have different skills of leading, each of these skills can only be applied depending on the nature of environment within which it operates and number of staff it has, therefore, leaders fail to study which leadership skills is applicable to the environment within which they operate. Based on this assertion, the study seeks to investigate the effect of leadership management skills on performance of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the effect of leadership management skills on performance of selected private hospital in Enugu metropolis. Specific objectives were to;

- i. examines the extent to which conflict resolution affect employee turnover of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.
- ii. ascertain the extent to which delegation affect employee productivity of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

The scope of the study covered effect of leadership management skills performance of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis. The study restricted only on staff basis of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis namely St. Mary's hospital & Maternity located at 10 John Nwodo GRA, St. Leos Hospital located at 57 Nike Lake Road Enugu, St. Patrick Hospital & Maternity located at 5 Ogbalu Street Independence Layout Enugu, Balm of Gilead Specialist Hospital Enugu located at Topland Road Enugu and Mother of Christ Specialist Hospital Enugu located at 20 Ogui Road, beside Holy Ghost Gathedral Enugu. The study also covered both dependent and independent variables. Meanwhile, dependent variable known as performance was broken into employee turnover and employee productivity while independent variable remains leadership management skills that were broken into conflict resolution and delegation.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Leadership

Leadership is defined as a process in which an individual influences other individuals or a group to achieve a specific goal. Leaders and followers must understand each other because leaders and followers are part of this process, it is important to address issues facing followers as have also issued facing leaders (Northhouse, 2016).

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Leadership is also defined as the process of influencing the activities of individuals and groups to move them administratively and guide them to achieve the goals of the organization, through effective communication and creating a spirit of creativity in individuals (Al-Sakarneh, 2020).

Management

Management is the process of achieving organizational performance through the efficient utilization of resources by planning, organising, leading and controlling. Effective management needs a set of skills like planning, communication, organization and leadership (Jennifer Herrity, 2023).

Skills

A skill is the learned ability to act with determined results with good execution often within a given amount of time, energy, or both. Skills can often be divided into domain-general and domain-specific skills. Some examples of general skills are time management, teamwork and leadership, and self-motivation (Jennifer Herrity, 2023).

Leadership Skills

Leadership skills are defined as the ability of the leader to perform the required tasks by transforming leadership knowledge into behavior in practical practices to achieve the required performance (Bich & Thai, 2019). Leadership skills are also defined as the capabilities possessed by the administrative leader to perform the leadership cycle in a way that ensures the performance of the tasks assigned to him/her efficiently and effectively and includes encouraging and influencing workers to achieve the desired goals (Jabareen, 2020).

Leadership Management Skills

Leadership management skills is the manner of approach to issues of the managers towards achieving the goals of their organization by transforming various resources like planning, organizing, directing, controlling and coordinating available to any organization into output through the functions of management (Field & Dubey, 2021).

Components of Leadership Management Skills that form Part of the Objectives of the Study

Conflict Resolution

Conflict resolution provides a pattern for managing and resolving disputes in a constructive and effective manner in order to maintain organizational aim and objectives (Adeniyi & Adelowo, 2024).

Delegation of Authority

Hasibuan (2017) refers to the transfer of some responsibility or decision-making power from the delegator (individual who has authority) to the delegate (individual who receives authority), allowing the delegate to act on behalf of the delegate.

Performance

Performance is also defined as it is the results, behavior, or activity that an individual shows during work or doing any kind of effort, and thus it is equal to the term achievement (Al-Labadi, 2015). Institutional performance is defined as the ability of the institution to achieve its objectives, increase interaction and cooperation among employees, confront accelerated environmental changes, and support competitiveness to ensure the stability and excellence of the organization (Al-Ajaleen, 2023).

Components of Performance that formed part of the Objectives of the Study

Employee Turnover

Employee turnover is the rotation of workers around the labour market; between firms, jobs and occupations; and between the states of employment and unemployment (Abassi & Hollman, 2020). Similarly, Price (2021)

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defines turnover as: the ratio of the number of organizational members who have left during the period being considered divided by the average number of people in that organization during the period. Employee turnover is defined in several ways due to diverse opinions but share a common view in the scholarly literature. Meanwhile, employee turnover is referred to as the rate at which people leave an organization, sometimes known as ‘labour turnover’, ‘wastage’, or ‘attrition’ (Armstrong, 2022).

Employee Productivity

Motowildo (2023), productivity is defined as the overall performance expected by an organization from the individual behavioral patterns exhibited by each worker within a specified timeframe. The significance of employee attitudes to management lies in their ability to shape the conduct of workers within the organizational context.

Conceptual Framework

This section shows connection link between dependent and independent variables, meanwhile, independent known as leadership management skills decomposed into conflict resolution and delegation of authority while performance remains dependent variable which was decomposed into employee turnover and employee productivity. Comprehensive diagrammatical illustration was demonstrated below;

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Model of Leadership Management Skills and Performance.

Source: Naif, et al. (2021). Strategic Leadership Skills and Their Impact on Organizational Commitment, A Prospective Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Employees in the General Company for Dairy Products, Iraqi Ministry of Industry, Journal of Business Economics for Applied Research, (1) – 6475 2709, Iraq.

Empirical Review

Conflict Resolution and Employee Turnover

Mariam, Uzochukwu, Gambo and Hauwa (2024) studied conflict management strategies and organisational performance: a study of federal roads maintenance Agency in Abuja, Nigeria. The objectives of this study are to determine the relationship between conflict management strategies specifically, avoidance strategy, collaboration strategy, compromising strategy, and accommodation strategy and organizational performance. The research design employed a survey research technique. The study found a significant positive relationship between organizational performance and all the examined conflict management strategies, namely avoidance strategy, collaboration strategy, accommodation strategy, and compromising strategy.

Adeniyi and Adelowo (2024) studied the transcendence of conflict resolution in society (social policy) and business organization in Nigeria. Through an interdisciplinary approach, the paper incorporates concepts such

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as social identity theory, organizational behavior, and strategic management. The study investigates how social structures, power dynamics, and cultural norms intersect with mindfulness, empathy, and affiliation to shape conflicts and inform conflict resolution practices in both societal and business contexts. By going beyond the conventional patterns, the paper aims to promote deeper understanding, empathy, and sustainable resolutions conducive to harmony and growth within communities and organizations.

Delegation of Authority and Employee Productivity

Akka, Ahmad and Yuniria (2024) examined delegation of authority and employee performance affect management decision making effectiveness in Nigeria. This study explores the relationship between effective Delegation of authority and employee performance, highlighting the importance of clear communication, trust-building, and well-defined responsibilities in managerial decision-making. findings indicate that (1) employee performance positively influences managerial decision-making, and (2) delegation positively influences managerial decision-making.

Ikputu, Gerry, Amah. and Amah (2024) conducted a study on delegation and employee engagement in Nigeria. This research was based on the theories of social exchange and leader-member exchange. The study advises that managers distribute jobs to employees based on their abilities, interests, and availability, and that they explain the task's significance to the individual.

Leadership Management Skills and Performance of Selected Private Hospitals

The study of Al-Faki and Nusari (2018), aimed to identify the most prominent leadership skills in public organizations, and to pay attention to the skills and development of workers at various levels that help them solve their problems and make the right decisions for the organization. The descriptive approach was used, and to collect field data, the questionnaire was used. The results of the study showed the importance of leadership skills and their role in improving the performance of public organizations.

The study of Thi Bich, and Le Thai (2019) aimed to study the effects of leadership skills on the performance of Vietnamese textile and clothing companies. The descriptive approach was used, and to collect field data, the questionnaire was used. The study reached several results, the most important of which is that leadership skills positively affect the performance of textile and clothing companies. The ranking of the most influential factors was: strategic skills, interpersonal skills, work skills, and cognitive skills.

The study of Muhammad, et al., (2020) examined the impact of the dimensions of strategic leadership skills on the performance of the accredited academic staff, which should be owned by the leaders of public universities in Kurdistan to achieve excellence and sustainability. The descriptive analytical approach was used, and information was collected through the questionnaire. The results indicated that there is a positive correlation between strategic leadership skills on the one hand and the performance of the accredited academic staff on the other hand.

While the study of Naif, et al., (2021) examined the relationship and impact between strategic leadership skills and organizational commitment, and the study relied on the descriptive approach, to collect field data, the questionnaire was used, and the study reached many results, the most important of which are: The presence of a positive and moral impact of leadership skills and their dimensions (technical skill, intellectual skill, human skill) on organizational commitment.

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Susilo, Furtasan and Uli (2022) examined the effect of leadership skills and training on employee performance by mediation of innovation capacity in glass manufacturing companies in Ghana. This study investigates the role that innovative capacity plays in the functioning of glass manufacturing businesses. The results showed that leadership, training and innovation capacity has a positive and significant effect on innovation capacity and employee performance.

The study of Al-Adwan (2023) sought to examine the impact of developing the leadership skills of public-school principals in light of digital transformation skills. The research relied on the descriptive approach and field data were collected using the questionnaire. The results showed that the digital transformation of public-school principals provides the necessary creative climate for the development, modernization, and sustainable professional development of principals, through which their capabilities, abilities, and leadership skills are refined.

The study of Desouky (2023) aimed to identify the effectiveness of the training program in the development of leadership skills and wisdom skills among the students of the Faculty of Education at Helwan University. The study relied on the experimental approach based on the experimental design with two groups (experimental control), and the study concluded that there is an impact of training programs based on the theory of successful intelligence on the development of leadership capabilities.

Maxwell, et al (2024) investigated leadership, and management style and influence on healthcare worker's job satisfaction and productivity in Nigeria. The main leadership styles identified were transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, laissez-faire leadership style and autocratic leadership style. Findings revealed that transformational leadership style has proven to positively influence job satisfaction and productivity while laissez-faire leadership demotivate healthcare workers.

Gap in Empirical Review

In the review of the literature, some of the literature related to the current study has been reviewed. In this regard studied leadership style and performance in other sector of the economy across global. In the same regard, previous researchers focused on survey design in line with relationship study but present study focused on survey design and effect study across all the objectives of the study. To the best knowledge of the researcher no one has researched on leadership management skills and performance of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis from period of 2023-2024 and this prompted the research to delve into this study.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted in the study was survey. Therefore, a survey research design was adopted, hence it makes possible for structured questionnaire usage, formulation and testing of hypotheses. Source of data was obtained directly from respondents through questionnaires, usually in the form of opinion subjects by individual or group, results from observation of something object activity, or events arranged in the form of statements or questions related to indicators of research variables, including leadership management skills and performance. In addition, both primary and secondary sources of data were captured, for secondary sources of data were obtained from several works of literature, like books, journals, magazines, social media, websites, and other relevant information still relevant to this research while primary sources of data were obtained from questionnaire issued to respondents. The target population is comprised of junior and senior staff of the five selected private

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hospitals in Enugu metropolis which were listed below in table 3.1. Then the total population of the study was 198.

S/N	Names of Private Hospitals	Address	Junior	Senior	Total
1	St. Mary’s hospital & Maternity	10 John Nwodo GRA,	18	13	31
2	St. Leos Hospital	57 Nike Lake Road Enugu	16	10	26
3	St. Patrick Hospital & Maternity	5 Ogbalu Street Independence Layout Enugu	23	17	40
4	Balm of Gilead Specialist Hospital Enugu	Topland Road Enugu	29	19	48
5	Mother of Christ Specialist Hospital Enugu	20 Ogui Road, beside Holy Ghost Gathedral Enugu	32	21	53
	Total		118	80	198

Source: Hospitals Internal Records, 2025

Determination of Sample Size

Since the population of the study is finite and small, purposively the researcher adopted the entire 198 as sample size determination.

Sampling Techniques

The study adopted convenience sampling for selecting the respondents since sampling frame was not available. Table 3.1 below shows the number of respondents selected in the study areas in each private hospitals in Enugu metropolis using Bowley’s (1976) proportionate allocation formular as follows: -

$$nh = \frac{n(Nh)}{N}$$

Where:

Nh = Group population from each stratum

n = overall sample size

N = the overall population

nh = sample size from each stratum, in this case each area in the State.

Table 2 Proportionate Allocation of the Questionnaire

S/N	Names of Private Hospitals	Total Population	Sample Size Distribution
1	St. Mary’s hospital & Maternity	31	31x198/198= 31
2	St. Leos Hospital	26	26x 198/198 = 26
3	St. Patrick Hospital & Maternity	40	40x198/198 = 40
4	Balm of Gilead Specialist Hospital Enugu	48	48x198/198 = 48
5	Mother of Christ Specialist Hospital Enugu	53	53x198/198 = 53
	Total	198	198

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Instrument for Data Collection

The instruments for data collection used in this research were a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire has two parts. All the questions in part A provides general information about the respondents while the remaining questions in part B address the research questions. Five-point Likert scale format was used to design the questionnaire with following structure, Very Great Extent [VGE] –5 points, Great Extent [GE] – 4 points, Undecided [UN] – 3 Points, Low Extent [LE] – 2 points and Very Low Extent [VLE] – 1 point

Validation of the Research Instrument

To make sure that the research instrument applied in this work is valid., a proper structuring of the questionnaire and a conduct of a pretest of every question contained in the questionnaire were carried out to ensure that they are valid. This was done by giving the questionnaire to management experts who modified the questionnaire and made the necessary corrections to ensure that it measure what it ought to measure. Also design of the questionnaire was made easy for the respondents to tick their preferred choices from the options provided as it has been established that the longer the length of questionnaire, the lower the response rate (Lavine, 1987).

Reliability of the Research Instrument

To ascertain that the instrument is reliable, a test-re-test method was adopted in which 15 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the hospitals studied. These were collected afterwards and re-distributed for the second time within period of two weeks. The outcome of the test-re-test was determined using spearman rank order correlation coefficient and the result gave a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.62$. The study employed regression analysis for testing hypotheses one and two.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Conflict resolution does not have significant positive effect on employee turnover of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

H_{a1}: Conflict resolution has significant positive effect on employee turnover of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Table 3 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.153a	.140	.131	.12617

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

Predictors: (Constant), conflict resolution table above revealed that there is a strong significant positive effect at $R = .153$ between conflict resolution and employee turnover. An examination of the table shows that R square = .140 which implies that conflict resolution accounts for 14% of variations having a significant positive effect on employee turnover.

Table 4 ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign
1 Regression	10.123	3	1.708	17.403	.000b
Residual	15.612	187	.142		
Total	25.735	190			

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

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a. Dependent Variable: employee turnover b. Predictors: (Constant), conflict resolution Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (17.403 divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.142), yielding $F=17.403$. From the results, the model in this table is statistically significant (Sig =.000). Therefore, conflict resolution had a significant positive effect on employee turnover at $F=17.403$.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Delegation does not have significant positive effect on employee productivity of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

H_{a2}: Delegation has significant positive effect on employee productivity of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Table 5 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.120a	.165	.147	.15468

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

Predictors: (Constant), delegation Table above revealed that there is a significant positive effect at $R = .120$ between delegation and employee productivity. An examination of the table shows that the R square = .163 which implies that delegation accounts for only 16% of variations having a significant positive effect on employee productivity of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Table 6 ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign
1 Regression	1.503	3	.134	1.035	.000b
Residual	17.417	187	.107		
Total	18.921	190			

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

a. Dependent Variable: employee productivity b. Predictors: (Constant), delegation Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (1.035) divided by the Mean Square Residual (.207), yielding $F=1.035$. The model in this table shows that delegation statistically and significantly at (Sig =.000) and had a significant positive effect on employee productivity at $F (1,035)$. The statistical results is given as; (delegation $p<0.05$). The statistical result implies that delegation has statistically significant positive effect on employee productivity of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One: Conflict resolution does not have significant positive effect on employee turnover of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (17.403 divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.142), yielding $F=17.403$. From the results, the model in this table is statistically significant (Sig =.000). Therefore, conflict resolution had a significant positive effect on employee turnover at $F (1,184) = 17.403$. This is in agreement with study of Mariam, Uzochukwu, Gambo and Hauwa (2024) studied conflict management

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strategies and organisational performance: a study of federal roads maintenance Agency in Abuja, Nigeria. The study found a significant positive relationship between organizational performance and all the examined conflict management strategies.

Hypothesis Two: Delegation does not have significant positive effect on employee productivity of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (1.035) divided by the Mean Square Residual (.107), yielding $F=1.035$. The model in this table shows that delegation statistically and significantly at ($Sig = .000$) and had a significant positive effect on employee productivity at $F(1,035)$. The study is based on study by Akka, Ahmad and Yuniria (2024) examined delegation of authority and employee performance affect management decision making effectiveness in Nigeria. This study explores the relationship between effective Delegation of authority and employee performance, highlighting the importance of clear communication, trust-building, and well-defined responsibilities in managerial decision-making. findings indicate that (1) employee performance positively influences managerial decision-making, and (2) delegation positively influences managerial decision-making.

Summary of Findings

- i. Conflict resolution had a significant positive effect on employee turnover of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis ($F=1,035, pv=.000<0.05$).
- ii. Delegation channel had a statistically significant positive effect on employee productivity selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis ($F=1,037, pv=.008<0.05$).

Conclusion

Effective leadership management skills is an important aspect as it usually enables the employees of the organizations to work efficiently and deliver excellent results. From the findings of the study, it can be concluded that leadership management skills had significant positive effect on performance of selected private hospitals in Enugu metropolis.

Recommendations

The study recommends the following based on the results:

- i. Hospital managers must not rely on their traditional ways of resolving conflict rather they provide modern ways of conflict resolution by initiating conflict resolve panel as a unit of the organization.
- ii. Hospital managers should extensively utilize delegation of authority system in their operation to enable them achieve effectively good ideals, quality knowledge and different skills within and outside workers.

Contributions to Knowledge

The contribution to knowledge of the study centered on connection link between dependent and independent variables;

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